

An Assessment of Grade 5 Learners' Reading Fluency in English at a Selected Primary School in Serenje District

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Abstract:

This study sought to assess the reading fluency of learners of a particular primary school in Serenje District since it was not known how fluent learners of a selected primary school were in reading and what contextual factors contributed to the reading fluency of the learners. Specifically, the objectives were: first, to assess grade 5 learners' reading fluency in English at a selected primary school in Serenje District and secondly, to explore factors affecting grade 5 learners' acquisition of reading fluency in English. The study employed a concurrent mixed methods design in which both qualitative and quantitative approaches were integrated. In total, the

study had 50 Grade 5 pupils (21 females and 29 males), 2 Grade 5 class teachers and 2 senior teachers for upper primary section at a selected school in Serenje District. The selected primary school was randomly sampled from the top five ranked schools in Ibolelo Zone of Serenje district. In this study, the researcher involved Grade 5 class teachers and senior teachers in upper primary in one-to-one interviews using semi-structured interviews. Grade 5 pupils' reading fluency was assessed using a standardised reading fluency test. The main findings of the study revealed that about 62 percent of grade 5 learners at the selected primary school were reading at frustration level in English. Additionally, the average Words Per Minute (WPM) was 44, the average Words Correct Per Minute (WCPM) was at 38, the average prosody score was 7 out of 16 points, average written comprehension score of 1 out of 5 marks. Further, the following factors positively affected grade 5 learners' acquisition of reading fluency in English: Reading practice, availability of teaching materials, differentiation in teaching, teacher quality, oral English proficiency, teacher-pupil rapport and methodology factors. Additionally, the following factors negatively affected grade 5 learners' acquisition of reading fluency in English: Limited instructional time, poor literacy backgrounds of learners, lack of teaching materials/resources, poor teacher quality, poor pupil quality, lack of parental support and policy. The study concluded that poor performance of grade 5 learners in reading fluency in English could be explained by a number of negative factors. The study recommends that the Ministry of Education should consider explicitly infusing reading fluency content in the Teacher Education curriculum for pre-service teachers so that teachers are prepared to teach reading fluency once deployed in primary schools.

Keywords: *Reading fluency, Words Correct Per Minute, prosody, frustration level.*

Introduction

Reading is a very important skill which is necessary for learning in school. Reading makes way for a better understanding of one's own experiences and it can be an exciting voyage to self-discovery (Panigrahi and Panda, 1996; Eyre, 2005; Mokatsi, 2005). Several studies assessing the literacy levels among Zambian children have shown that reading levels in Zambia were exceptionally low. Without the ability to use reading and writing to engage in a variety of ways of thinking, learners will be incapable of communicating and surviving in this print-based education system and society (Sharma, 1974; Williams, 1998; National Reading Committee, 1997; SACMEQ, 1995, 1998, 2006, 2008, 2010; Serpell and Kanyika, 1999; Nkamba and Kanyika, 1998).

Studies by Kanyika (2003); MOE 2006, 2008; and Sampa, 2005) on the reading levels among Zambian learners have shown that overall, reading achievement levels were still low and the mean performance was below the set standard in Zambian languages and English. For instance, MOE (2006) revealed that by province, the trends indicated a constant performance between 1999 and 2006 in reading in English. The mean performance in English reading at Grade 5 level indicated that reading levels between 1999 and 2006 were relatively the same with 33.2 percent in 1999, 33.4 percent in 2001, 33.9 percent in 2003 and 34.5 percent in 2006 (Zambia National Assessment Survey, 2006; Chibamba, 2012). Later studies by Kanyika et al. (2008) also reported that generally by province, the mean performance at Grade 5 level in reading in English was 35.3 percent. This showed stagnation in pupils' performance when compared to the 2006 survey results which were at 34.50 percent in English. The mean performance is below the criterion percentage mark of 40.0 percent for minimum level of performance set for the nation in English (MOE, 2008).

The Southern and Eastern Africa Consortium for Monitoring Educational Quality (SACMEQ) has also been concerned about the low literacy levels in Zambia. A study conducted by

SACMEQ revealed that 25% of Grade 6 pupils could not read at a minimum level of proficiency and only 3% could read at a specified desirable level (MOE, 1995). To explain and justify these low literacy levels, the same study highlighted a number of reasons, one of which was the use of an unfamiliar language (English) when teaching literacy. This language factor was seen to be the major reason for most Zambian children's backwardness in reading and writing skills (Kelly, 1995; MOE, 1996; Sampa, 2003; Williams, 1995; Kachinga, 2012).

An assessment survey conducted by the Examinations Council of Zambia on behalf of the Ministry of Education revealed that reading performance on the English test was poor. Generally, learners revealed deficiencies in reading and comprehension skills (ECZ, 2006). This meant that despite the language of initial literacy instruction being familiar to the learners the reading performance was still poor. Clearly, despite government and other stakeholders working hard, very little success has been achieved on literacy levels among learners, especially at Basic school level (Matafwali, 2010, Mubanga, 2012; Mwanza, 2012; Kachinga, 2012).

Arising from the concerns raised by different stakeholders as manifested by the different studies cited in the preceding paragraphs, the Ministry of Education in 2013 developed the National Literacy Framework. The purpose of the Zambian National Literacy Framework was to establish a set of guidelines for teaching and learning literacy in all Zambian schools (MOE, 2013). This brought in Primary Literacy Programme (PLP) where regional local languages were to be used as media of instruction in all subjects from Grades 1-4. This was due to discontentment with the Primary Reading Programme (PRP) where Zambian local languages were used as medium of instruction for the first year of primary schooling and English took over from grade two.

The National Literacy Framework (NLF) (2013) notes that instruction in the local language at the foundation stage will support learners as they progress towards English. This means initial

literacy at Grades 1 and 2 would be provided in local languages, learners would also be introduced to oral English at Grade 2 and later reading and writing in English at Grades 3 and 4. The National Literacy Framework (NLF) (2013) further outlines that the PLP is anchored on five key competences namely Phonic Awareness, Phonics, Fluency, Vocabulary and Comprehension. Phonic Awareness is the ability to hear sounds and manipulate them orally, put sounds together, break words apart into sounds, identify rhyming words, identify likenesses and differences in spoken words. Phonics is the ability to put written letters and their sounds together. Fluency is the ability to read a text with accuracy, speed and expression and understanding. Vocabulary is the ability to understand the meaning of words and use them orally and in writing. Comprehension is the ability to understand the meaning of what is read or heard (The National Reading Panel Report, 2000; Kuhn & Stahl, 2003; The National Literacy Framework (NLF), 2013).

The National Literacy Framework (2013) stressed the four reading fluency elements: accuracy, rate, prosody, and meaning in explicit fluency instruction for learners to attain high level of fluency (MESVTEE, 2013).

This study focused more on reading fluency in English in Zambia and concentrated on the four components of reading fluency namely accuracy, rate, expression (prosody) and comprehension.

Statement of the Problem

Fluency is a foundational reading skill and an essential component for proficient reading. Lack of reading proficiency prevents one from adequately comprehending the texts. If fluency problems are not addressed in the early elementary grades, it is likely that these problems will continue to hinder learners reading progress in subsequent years (Rasinski, Paige, Rain, Stewart, Julovich, Prenkert, Rupley, & Nichols, 2017). Against this background, studies have been conducted to assess literacy abilities of learners in Zambia. However, these studies have been surveys which have reported data on a large scale. This means that while national literacy levels are known in Zambia, there was no school

based literacy performance data to report how specific schools perform and what contextual factors contribute to the literacy abilities of learners. In other words, there is very limited and scanty school data on reading fluency in English in the Zambian context. Hence, this study sought to assess the reading fluency of learners of a particular primary school in Serenje District since it was not known how fluent learners of a selected primary school were in reading in English and what contextual factors contributed to the reading fluency of the learners. As a question, the research problem was; how fluent were grade 5 learners in reading in English and what factors contributed to the learners reading fluency?

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study were to:

- a. assess grade 5 learners' reading fluency in English at a selected primary school in Serenje District.
- b. explore factors affecting grade 5 learners' acquisition of reading fluency in English at a selected primary school in Serenje District.

Methods and Materials

The study used the concurrent mixed methods design grounded in a Pragmatism paradigm or pragmatist paradigm. This is the research design in which both qualitative and quantitative approaches are integrated (Milingo, 1999; Milingo, 2004; Milingo, Changwe and Hara-Zulu, 2021). The study population comprised all grade 5 pupils, all grade 5 teachers and all senior teachers at a selected school in Serenje District. The total sample was 54 and it comprised the following participants 50 Grade 5 pupils (21 girls and 29 boys), 2 Grade 5 teachers and 2 senior teachers for upper primary section at a selected school in Serenje District. Purposive and simple random sampling techniques were used. The selected primary school was randomly sampled from the top five ranked schools in Ibolelo Zone of Serenje district. Purposive sampling procedure was used to select the Grade 5 pupils, Grade 5 teachers and senior teachers at a

selected school in Serenje District. Purposive sampling was used to select the respondents under study because they were expected to have knowledge on the subject. Grade 5 pupils were involved because they would have completed Grade 3 and 4 Literacy in English instruction under the Primary Literacy Programme (PLP) as guided by the National Literacy Framework of 2013. The rationale of purposive sampling is premised on selecting participants who would provide the richest information for in-depth analysis related to the central issue under study (Kombo & Tromp, 2006). In this study, the researcher involved Grade 5 class teachers and senior teachers in upper primary in one-to-one interviews using semi-structured interview guides. Grade 5 learners reading fluency was assessed using a standardised reading fluency Words Correct Per Minute (WPCM) assessment. A standardised reading fluency WPCM assessment was employed on Grade 5 learners. An English language passage was extracted from a Grade 5 reader under the Zambia Primary Course (ZPC). This was used as a reading text to determine the reading fluency of Grade 5 learners at a selected school in Serenje District. Qualitative data was analysed thematically by categorising the information into significant themes. Data collected through interviews was organised and coded by research questions into themes. The data was interpreted and discussed. Quantitative data on reading fluency accuracy and rate as well as prosody and comprehension were converted into tables, frequencies and percentages using Microsoft Excel and Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). Ethics were observed through informed consent and anonymity of respondents.

Data Presentation

This section presents research findings both quantitatively and qualitatively. Data has been presented under research objectives. Quantitative data is presented arising from the Words Per Minute (WPM), Words Correct Per Minute (WCPM) and prosody standardised assessments as well as written comprehension on Grade 5 learners while qualitative data is

presented arising from the use of semi-structured one-to-one interviews with class and senior teachers. The findings are therefore, presented in line with the following research objectives.

- Assess Grade 5 learners' reading fluency in English at a selected primary school in Serenje District.
- Explore factors affecting Grade 5 learners' acquisition of reading fluency in English at a selected primary school in Serenje District.

Assess Grade 5 Learners' Reading Fluency in English at a Selected Primary School in Serenje District

The first objective sought to assess Grade 5 learners' reading fluency in English at a selected primary school in Serenje District. To collect data on objective number one, the Grade 5 pupils were assessed in reading fluency in English using a standardised reading fluency Words Per Minute (WPM), Words Correct Per Minute (WCPM) and prosody standardised assessments as well as written comprehension. Since reading fluency has different components, data will be presented under different aspects of reading fluency. The data will concentrate on the four components of reading fluency namely accuracy, rate, prosody (expression) and comprehension. The reading fluency in English data will be presented under sub-headings. This section will further present the reading fluency data of the four components in tables 1a and 1b to tables 4a and 4b on reading fluency in English.

Findings on reading fluency word accuracy assessment – Quantitative data

The study had a total of 50 grade 5 learners, 21 females and 29 males who were subjected to a timed one-minute reading fluency assessment on a cold read or unpractised passage that had 305 words. The reading accuracy data for each learner was arrived at by subtracting the number of errors from the number of words read per learner divided by the total number of words read, then the answer was multiplied by 100 to get a percentage. The percentage word accuracy of each learner can either fall into independent,

instruction or frustration reading level. The word accuracy percentage is obtained by dividing the Words Correct Per Minute (WCPM) of each learner into the total words read per minute (WPM or reading rate) multiplied by 100. Learners at independent reading level are those who score between 95-100 % in word accuracy. Learners at instructional reading level are those who score between 90-94 % word accuracy

while learners at frustration reading level are those who score between 0-89 % word accuracy.

The data on performance of learners in word accuracy is presented in tables 1a and 1b below. Table 1a shows the raw data of all the 50 learners' performances in accuracy while table 1b shows the categorised and summarised learners' accuracy performance data.

Table 1a. Field Data on 50 Grade 5 Pupils' Performance in Word Accuracy in English

S/N	Learner Code	Gender	Word Accuracy
1	L17	F	0
2	L27	M	0
3	L41	M	0
4	L43	M	0
5	L48	M	0
6	L47	M	9
7	L24	M	13
8	L9	F	20
9	L10	F	20
10	L33	M	28
11	L12	F	53
12	L44	M	57
13	L16	F	59
14	L23	M	60
15	L20	F	67
16	L3	F	71
17	L4	F	71
18	L32	M	76
19	L15	F	77
20	L18	F	77
21	L46	M	78
22	L34	M	78
23	L50	M	79
24	L35	M	81
25	L28	M	81
26	L42	M	83
27	L45	M	83
28	L13	F	85
29	L30	M	85
30	L29	M	89
31	L2	F	89
32	L14	F	90
33	L8	F	91
34	L31	M	91
35	L11	F	91
36	L37	M	91
37	L38	M	92
38	L1	F	92
39	L22	M	93
40	L39	M	93
41	L21	F	94

42	L49	M	95
43	L7	F	96
44	L19	F	96
45	L6	F	97
46	L25	M	97
47	L5	F	97
48	L36	M	99
49	L26	M	99
50	L40	M	100
Average			69

As noted in table 1a above, the raw data of all the 50 learners' performances in accuracy is ranked from smallest (0%) to highest (100%). On average, the last row in yellow notes that the

50 learners' average score was 69%. The data in 1a is further categorised and summarised in 1b above.

Table 1b. Grade 5 Pupils' Word Accuracy in English

Text Level	Word Accuracy (%)	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Independent Level	95-100	9	18	18	18
Instructional Level	90 – 94	10	20	20	38
Frustration Level	0 – 89	31	62	62	100
Total		50	100		

As shown in table 1b above, 18 percent of the grade 5 learners were at independent reading level (between 95-100 % word accuracy score), 20 percent of the grade 5 learners were at instructional reading level (between 90-94 % word accuracy score) while 62 percent of the grade 5 learners were at frustration reading level (between 0-89 % word accuracy score).

Findings on reading fluency prosody assessment - Quantitative data

The reading prosody data for each learner was arrived at by rating each learner using a prosody fluency rubric which has four parameters namely; pace, smoothness, phrasing as well as

expression and volume. Each of these parameters has up to a maximum of 4 points on the scale. This meant each learner was rated out of 16 points. If a learner scored 10 or more it indicates that the learner was making good progress in fluency. Scores below 10 indicate that the learner needed additional instruction in fluency.

The data on performance of learners in reading prosody is presented in tables 2a and 2b below. Table 2a shows the raw data of all the 50 learners' performance in reading prosody while table 2b shows the categorised and summarised learners' reading prosody performance data.

Table 2a. Field Data on 50 Grade 5 Pupils' Performance in Prosody out of 16

S/N	Learner Code	Gender	Prosody (Out of 16)
1	L3	F	4
2	L4	F	4
3	L9	F	4
4	L10	F	4
5	L12	F	4
6	L16	F	4
7	L17	F	4
8	L20	F	4

9	L23	M	4
10	L24	M	4
11	L27	M	4
12	L33	M	4
13	L41	M	4
14	L43	M	4
15	L44	M	4
16	L45	M	4
17	L47	M	4
18	L48	M	4
19	L15	F	5
20	L28	M	5
21	L34	M	5
22	L35	M	5
23	L42	M	6
24	L32	M	7
25	L46	M	7
26	L8	F	8
27	L13	F	8
28	L18	F	8
29	L22	M	8
30	L29	M	8
31	L30	M	8
32	L37	M	8
33	L2	F	9
34	L11	F	9
35	L14	F	9
36	L31	M	9
37	L38	M	9
38	L50	M	9
39	L6	F	10
40	L7	F	10
41	L25	M	11
42	L39	M	11
43	L1	F	12
44	L5	F	12
45	L19	F	12
46	L21	F	12
47	L36	M	12
48	L49	M	12
49	L26	M	14
50	L40	M	14
Average			7

As noted in table 2a above, the raw data of all the 50 learners' performance in prosody out of 16 is ranked from lowest (4) to highest (16). On average, the last row in yellow notes that the 50

learners' average score in prosody out of 16 was 7. The data in 2a is further categorised and summarised in 2b above.

Table 2b. Grade 5 Pupil's Reading Fluency Prosody Scores in English

Prosody Score	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
4	18	36	36	36
5	4	8	8	44
6	1	2	2	46

7	2	4	4	50
8	7	14	14	64
9	6	12	12	76
10	2	4	4	80
11	2	4	4	84
12	6	12	12	96
13	0	0	0	96
14	2	4	4	100
15	0	0	0	100
16	0	0	0	100
Total	50	100		

Table 2a shows that 36 percent of the Grade 5 learners scored 4 points, 8 percent scored 5 points, 2 percent scored 6 points, 4 percent scored 7 points, 14 percent scored 8 points while 12 percent of the learners scored 9 points. Furthermore, 4 percent of the learners scored 10 points, 4 percent scored 11 points, 12 percent scored 12 points, 0 percent scored 13 points and 4 percent of the learners scored 14 points. Additionally, the table also indicates that 0 percent (none) of the learners scored 15 and 16 points on the prosody scale.

Findings on reading fluency comprehension assessment – Quantitative data

The reading comprehension score data for each learner was arrived at by subjecting each learner to five (5) short answer, written reading comprehension questions in English. The

questions ranged from literal to inference. Each learner's answer script was marked out of 5 marks. Each of the five (5) questions given in this task had 1 mark thereby giving a total score of 5 marks. The task used a Zambia Primary Course (ZPC) Grade 5 passage because it was carefully graded by the Curriculum Development Centre (CDC) to be suitable for Grade 5.

The data on performance of learners in written reading comprehension out of 5 is presented in tables 3a and 3b below. Table 3a shows the field data of all the 50 learners' performance in reading comprehension out of 5 while table 3b shows the categorised and summarised learners' reading comprehension out of 5 performance data.

Table 3a. Field Data on 50 Grade 5 Pupils' Performance in Comprehension out of 5

S/N	Learner Code	Gender	Comprehension (Out of 5)
1	L9	F	0
2	L10	F	0
3	L12	F	0
4	L14	F	0
5	L15	F	0
6	L17	F	0
7	L18	F	0
8	L20	F	0
9	L23	M	0
10	L27	M	0
11	L28	M	0
12	L33	M	0
13	L35	M	0
14	L37	M	0
15	L41	M	0
16	L43	M	0
17	L44	M	0

18	L45	M	0
19	L46	M	0
20	L47	M	0
21	L48	M	0
22	L50	M	0
23	L21	F	1
24	L49	M	1
25	L1	F	2
26	L3	F	2
27	L4	F	2
28	L7	F	2
29	L8	F	2
30	L11	F	2
31	L16	F	2
32	L19	F	2
33	L22	M	2
34	L24	M	2
35	L29	M	2
36	L32	M	2
37	L34	M	2
38	L38	M	2
39	L39	M	2
40	L40	M	2
41	L2	F	3
42	L13	F	3
43	L25	M	3
44	L30	M	3
45	L31	M	3
46	L42	M	3
47	L6	F	4
48	L26	M	4
49	L5	F	5
50	L36	M	5
AVERAGE			1

As noted in table 3a above, the field data of all the 50 learners' performance in written comprehension out of 5 marks is ranked from lowest (0) to highest (5). On average, the last row

in yellow notes that the 50 learners' average score in written comprehension out of 5 was 1 mark. The data in 4a is further categorised and summarised in 3b below.

Table 3b. Grade 5 Pupil's Reading Fluency Comprehension Scores in English

Comprehension Score	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
0	22	44	44	44
1	2	4	4	48
2	16	32	32	80
3	6	12	12	92
4	2	4	4	96
5	2	4	4	100
Total	50	100		

As shown in table 3b above, 44 percent scored 0 marks, 4 percent scored 1 mark, 32 percent scored 2 marks, 12 percent scored 3 marks, 4

percent scored 4 marks while 4 percent of the grade 5 learners in the study scored 5 marks in the reading comprehension assessment.

Findings on reading fluency reading rate assessment – Quantitative data

The reading rate data for each learner was arrived at by counting the total number of words each learner was able to read within a given time of 1 minute or 60 seconds. This is called Words Per Minute (WPM) or rate. Rate does not pay attention to the mistakes or errors made by the

learner while reading. The passage used for this task had 305 words.

The data on performance of learners in reading rate (WPM) is presented in tables 4a and 4b below. Table 4a shows the raw data of all the 50 learners' performance in reading rate (WPM) while table 4b shows the categorised and summarised learners' reading rate (WPM) performance data.

Table 4a. Field Data on 50 Grade 5 Pupils' Performance in Total Words Per Minute (WPM)

S/N	Learner Code	Gender	Words Per Minute
1	L41	M	4
2	L17	F	6
3	L43	M	6
4	L48	M	6
5	L24	M	8
6	L27	M	8
7	L9	F	10
8	L10	F	10
9	L23	M	10
10	L47	M	11
11	L13	F	13
12	L16	F	17
13	L33	M	18
14	L12	F	19
15	L4	F	21
16	L44	M	23
17	L45	M	24
18	L20	F	27
19	L28	M	27
20	L3	F	28
21	L34	M	32
22	L18	F	35
23	L15	F	39
24	L32	M	41
25	L42	M	41
26	L2	F	46
27	L30	M	46
28	L35	M	47
29	L1	F	49
30	L46	M	49
31	L29	M	53
32	L8	F	55
33	L31	M	55
34	L50	M	57
35	L11	F	58
36	L22	M	58
37	L37	M	58
38	L14	F	59
39	L6	F	60
40	L25	M	60

41	L38	M	60
42	L5	F	71
43	L39	M	75
44	L40	M	75
45	L19	F	81
46	L49	M	81
47	L36	M	99
48	L26	M	105
49	L7	F	113
50	L21	F	132
Average			44

As noted in table 4a above, the raw data of all the 50 learners' performance in total Words Per Minute (WPM) is ranked from lowest (4) to highest (132). On average, the last row in yellow

notes that the 50 learners' average score in total Words Per Minute (WPM) was 44. The data in 4a is further categorised and summarised in 4b below.

Table 4b. Grade 5 Pupil's Fluency Reading Rate Scores in English

Reading Rate (Wpm)	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
100 - 149	3	6	6	6
50 - 99	17	34	34	40
0 - 49	30	60	60	100
Total	50	100		

Table 4b indicates that 6 percent of the Grade 5 pupils' fluency reading rate (WPM) scores in English were clustered between 100-149, 34 percent of the pupils' reading rate (WPM) scores in English were clustered between 50 – 99 while 60 percent of the Grade 5 pupils' fluency reading rate scores in English were clustered between 0 - 49.

Explore Factors Affecting Grade 5 Learners' Acquisition of Reading Fluency in English at a Selected Primary School in Serenje District

The second objective sought to explore factors affecting grade 5 learners' acquisition of reading fluency in English at a selected primary school in Serenje District. Face to face interviews were used to collect the data. The following is the data presented under positive and negative factors.

Factors that positively affected grade 5 learners' acquisition of reading fluency in English

According to the findings of the study, some factors that positively affected grade 5 learners' acquisition of reading fluency in English include

the following: Practice factor, materials factor, methodology factor, teacher factor, oral English factor, teacher-pupil rapport factor and differentiation factor.

a. Practice factor

Teacher 1 had this to say:

Giving them a lot of activities to do with reading and also making them take part in reading. When giving activities, assigning learners to be doing more of reading. And also encouraging them to make stories, imaginal stories and then they write them, they also give them to others also to read them. (Teacher 1)

b. Materials factor

Similarly, teacher 2 had this to say:

What encourages reading in English, maybe the picture, for example if you get the book, the picture, and the cover of the book. What the learners will see on the cover page will make learners be interested to read what is inside the book or the materials the teacher is using to teach reading, learners will be able to grasp that concept

but if always you just write on the board learners don't concentrate. (Teacher 2)

Additionally, teacher 3 had this to say:

And even the teaching and learning aids they are also helping to stick vowels, and words just in class, English words. Learners will be forced to start reading. So teaching aids also help. Even a programme where on a particular day learners can just watch anything or any lesson concerning English or something that can encourage learners to admire something through watching. These private schools, others especially the babies they watch cartoons, their friends are speaking English. (Teacher 3)

Teacher 4 had this to say:

I would say availability of storybooks, teaching and learning aids, aids which have pictures trying to tell a story. (Teacher 4)

c. Methodology factor

When probed further, teacher 4 had this to say:

Maybe I should also mention to say even the method applied also may help learners to know how to read English well. If we were to use the phonics, the methods that we used to use especially when we were using the Break Through To Literacy and Step In To English (SITE) in grade 2, like when we use the phonic methods, the syllabic method to mention but a few. (Teacher 4)

d. Teacher factor

At least, you bring different activities for the learners. Motivation from teachers, the way a teacher will deliver the lesson, will encourage learners to put much effort. (Teacher 2)

e. Oral English factor

Teacher 3 had this to say:

Speaking of English, just the speaking itself. We are just fond of Bemba, Bemba (Zambian Languages (ZL)). So I think even just the speaking itself one if somebody is encouraged to speak English that person will be also forced to start reading English to know the words. (Teacher 3)

f. Teacher-pupil rapport factor

Teacher 4 had this to say:

And also the relationship between the teacher and the learners. These are some of the factors that encourage reading English in learners. (Teacher 4)

g. Differentiation factor

At least, you bring different activities for the learners. Motivation from teachers, the way a teacher will deliver the lesson, will encourage learners to put much effort. (Teacher 2)

Factors that negatively affect grade 5 learners' acquisition of reading fluency in English

In the same vein, according to the findings of the study, factors that negatively affected grade 5 learners' acquisition of reading fluency in English include the following: Time factor, background factor, materials/resources factor, environmental factor, teacher factor, pupil factor, transition factor, parental factor and policy factor.

a. Limited Time

Teacher 1 had this to say:

Time specifically for reading, to learn reading we don't have. Mainly, reading is learnt through comprehension and also as they are doing these activities they are reading (Teacher 1).

b. Learners' Background

I think also the foundation. English, like this time considering our new curriculum, reading in English is done in grade 5 (Teacher 1).

For instance, Mwasankano, Kawama, Chilisha, Chansa to mention but a few and it's like these learners actually most of them were deprived of the opportunity of passing through preschool. So, it is really a challenge. But for a few learners who at least had an opportunity to pass through preschool, they are able to catch up very fast (Teacher 4).

c. Lack of materials/resources

I think also lack of material, maybe stories, story books (Teacher 1).

In addition, teacher 4 had this to say on materials:

Lack of books, especially the story books including the pupils' books in school. We have a shortfall of that, so it is usually a challenge, whereby you only depend on decodable stories for stories. But if we had a lot of story books it was going to be helpful even on the part of learners (Teacher 4).

d. Poor literacy environment

Teacher 2 had this to say:

Among our learners, maybe the catchment area, you will find that children from Chilibsha far, far places from the town they find it difficult to read English or just speak English. When you just start teaching English uummm it's a challenge for them. so at least those who are maybe coming within the boma we don't find most challenges but children from far places (Teacher 2).

Teacher 3 continues to highlight some negative factors and she had this to say:

Sometimes even the environment. What I have discovered is that those learners who come from homes where they speak English they don't find difficulties because in my class I have some of the learners, daughters and sons of teachers and lecturers, mostly they are the ones who do better in English. But these others who are just coming from typical villages that's something we can't control (Teacher 3).

e. Teacher factor

Additionally, teacher 2 continued highlighting some issues negatively affecting learners and had this to say:

Even us teachers we can be a problem sometimes causing the learners not to read fluently. We will rely much on those children who are well to do instead of focusing on those children coming from villages. And when we are giving, maybe, the textbooks to the learners to go and read at home, we find that again we give those who know how to read instead of giving those learners who are not able to read (Teacher 2).

f. Pupil factor

Regarding pupil factor as one of the hindering factors, teacher 4 had this to say:

Maybe because most of the learners that we have especially in our school they come from places where maybe they are not introduced to English. So, sometimes as you teach them it is a bit easier to teach someone who understands what they are even reading but in our case because of our learners coming from places where they rarely speak English, it is a bit difficult (Teacher 4).

g. Transition from using local language to English

Teacher 3 had this to say:

I think the crossing over from Icibemba (ZL) to English is challenging. I think maybe it would have been better if English would have been started just at preschool bit by bit where they are learning side by side Icibemba (ZL) and English better they just begin from the word go. English should be taught side by side with Icibemba (ZL). In fact, in grade 4 we discourage answering words in Bemba (ZL) or writing spellings in Bemba (ZL) so crossing over at grade 4 level is somehow difficult (Teacher 3).

h. Parental factor

Teacher 2 had this to say:

When they go home, parents don't know how to speak English or even to write in Bemba. So maybe you teach them at school, they go home there they have no that allowance to speak English with parents at home even their siblings at home because their parents are not learned people (Teacher 2).

i. Inappropriate language Policy

In the same vein, teacher 4 continued to highlight some issues negatively affecting learners and had this to say:

The introduction of teaching Icibemba (ZL) has hindered because what I have discovered is that the concentration is done much on teaching learners how to read in Icibemba (ZL) or any other local language. So for the learners no much time is given to introduction of reading in English, so for the learners to break though in English is much of a challenge unless you apply more and more effort (Teacher 4).

Data Analysis

The findings will be discussed with a special reference to the results obtained from grade 5 learners' reading fluency assessment in English as well as class and senior teachers' one-to-one interviews. The following are the sub themes based on the research objectives: Assess grade 5 learners' reading fluency in English at a selected primary school in Serenje District, and to explore factors affecting grade 5 learners' acquisition of reading fluency in English at a selected primary school in Serenje District.

Assess Grade 5 Learners' Reading Fluency in English at a Selected Primary School in Serenje District

The first objective sought to assess Grade 5 learners' reading fluency in English at a selected primary school in Serenje District. The findings of the study based on quantitative data gathered through interacting with each grade 5 learner per minute and later through a follow up written reading comprehension assessment on 305-worded passage revealed that, about 62 percent of grade 5 learners at the selected primary school were reading at frustration level in English. Additionally, the average Words Per Minute (WPM) was at 44, the average Words Correct Per Minute (WCPM) was at 38, the average prosody score was 7 out of 16 points and the average written comprehension score was 1 out of 5 marks.

The findings in the sub-heading above which highlighted the various parameters of reading fluency (rate, accuracy, prosody and comprehension) were consistent with the teacher respondents' perspectives that indicated that the reading levels of their learners were between average and below average. For instance, the average prosody score which stood at 7 out of 16 is deemed low and is consistent with Rasinski's Multidimensional Fluency Scale used to assess the level of student's prosodic reading. To determine the level of prosodic reading, the students with range scores between 4 and 7 were considered as *low*, while students with range score between 8 and 12 were considered as *moderate* while students with range

score between 13 and 16 were considered as *high* (Rahmawati, Rosmalina, & Anggraini, 2020).

From the data in paragraph 1 of this chapter, about 62 percent of grade 5 learners at the selected primary school were reading at frustration level in English. The average word accuracy level was at 69%. This means the word accuracy percentage was between 0-89%. The implication is that if a child's accuracy rate is below 90%, then they are at the frustration reading level. As its name implies, a passage or text at this level is too difficult and would most likely frustrate the child and impair comprehension.

This is at variance with earlier studies in the USA where students in the 5th grade were required to read at a rate of 110 words correct per minute (Hasbrouck & Tindal, 2006) or below with an accuracy rate between 90% and 94% accuracy (Bear et al., 2007). A student in the 6th grade needed to read at a rate of 127 words correct per minute (Hasbrouck & Tindal, 2006) or below with an accuracy rate between 90% and 94% accuracy (Bear et al., 2007; Kalis, 2012). Later studies by (Hasbrouck & Tindal, 2017) have put the average WCPM at 150 for a Grade 5 child.

Similarly, Piper, Schroeder, & Trudell (2016) citing works from Harris and Sipay as well as Hasbrouck and Tindal contend that researchers in the USA set the benchmark for English oral reading fluency needed for comprehension at 60–90 WCPM in Grade 1, 85–120 WCPM in Grade 2 and 115–140 in Grade 3 WCPM. This revelation has very serious implications for the findings of this study because 60% of the learners were only able to read between 0-49 WCPM. In this regard, it is not surprising to note that the Grade 5 learners in this study did not do well in comprehension too because they fell far short of the minimum required even for a Grade 1 child to comprehend. This view is further amplified by the following quote from the National Reading Panel.

Accuracy in reading supports students in becoming more proficient readers, because if reading is labourious and inefficient, it will be difficult for the child to remember what has been read and relate

those ideas to their background knowledge and experiences (NRP, 2000, p11).

Furthermore, it is of concern that about 60% of the grade 5 learners in this study were only able to read between 0-49 Words Correct Per Minute (WCPM) or an average of 38 WCPM in English. This is also at variance with the average reading levels of Grade 5 learners in South Africa whose benchmark ranged between 90-100 WCPM in English (Spaull, 2015) and the benchmark range for American Grade 5 learners who stood between 130-150 WCPM in English (Hasbrouck and Tindal, 2006; 2017).

Furthermore, the findings of this study are further at variance with even the Philippines Grade 3 reading benchmark that was around 60 WCPM (National EGRA report, 2019). Compared to some Zambian grade 5 learners at the selected school, the grade 3 learners in Philippines were doing relatively better in English. In another study, Piper, Schroeder, and Trudell (2016) assessed 2,000 students in Kenya in standard (grade) 3 to determine if children read more fluently in English, Kiswahili or mother tongue (Dholuo and Gikuyu) using an EGRA tool developed in Kenya. The data showed that in Central Province, children read more fluently in English (40.2 WCPM) than in Kiswahili (26.7 WCPM) and that children read more fluently in English (40.2 WCPM) than in Gikuyu (20.0 WCPM). In Nyanza Province, the results showed that children read more fluently in English (25.6 WCPM) than in Kiswahili (19.0 WCPM) and in English (25.6 WCPM) than in Dholuo (19.6 WCPM) (Piper, Schroeder, & Trudell, 2016). The findings from Kenya in terms of WCPM in English are almost close to the average WCPM of 38 or range of 0-49 WCPM in this study except this study was focusing on English for Grade 5 learners at a selected school. The other link to this study is that the average WCPM in English in Kenya was almost comparable to the average findings of this study.

The dismal performance by Grade 5 learners in this study is consistent with national mean performance in English reading at Grade 5 between 1999 and 2008 standing at 33.2 percent

in 1999, 33.4 percent in 2001, 33.9 percent in 2003 and 34.5 percent in 2006 (Zambia National Assessment Survey, 2006; Chibamba, 2012) and later studies by Kanyika et al. (2008) at 35.3 percent. The mean performance is still below the criterion percentage mark of 40.0 percent for minimum level of performance set for the nation in English (MOE, 2008).

The few grade 5 learners that seemingly did well in prosody score that is between 10 to 16 points and those who scored highly in comprehension as well as in Words Per Minute (WPM) and Words Correct Per Minute (WCPM) could be attributed to learners whose parents were very supportive particularly children of teachers and lecturers as indicated by teacher respondents. This would be discussed further under factors in objective 2 of this study.

Furthermore, the dismal performance of learners in the various components of reading fluency in this study were also consistent with the perspectives of respondents who indicated that they had no college or university training in reading fluency except through Continuing Professional Development (CPDs). Additionally, teacher respondents raised concern about some teachers who had a negative attitude towards handling grades 5-7 learners because they did not want to handle English language which required them to exert more effort for their learners to breakthrough in English.

The dismal written reading comprehension results were also not surprising because respondents indicated that one of the challenges they faced were learners reading without understanding as well as mispronouncing of words. This reading without understanding was also not surprising because the grade 5 learners' performance in prosody left much to be desired. A number of them read without expressivity and some just read word for word or could not even decode any word in English.

This was also consistent with the teacher respondents who lamented about the challenges they had from some of their learners whose parents were not supportive and resided in the marginalised rural and peri-urban areas of the district under study. Some of these learners did

not even have some siblings to assist. In the same vein, teacher respondents lamented about learners in grade 5 who have not had a chance to attend preschool.

Explore Factors Affecting Grade 5 Learners' Acquisition of Reading Fluency in English at a Selected Primary School in Serenje District

The second research objective of this study sought to explore factors affecting grade 5 learners' acquisition of reading fluency in English at a selected primary school in Serenje District. The teacher respondents who were engaged in one-to-one interviews highlighted the following negative and positive factors that affected grade 5 learners' acquisition of reading fluency in English. Regarding objective number 2, the respondents highlighted the following factors that positively affected grade 5 learners' acquisition of reading fluency in English which include: Practice factor, materials factor, differentiation factor, teacher factor, oral English factor, teacher-pupil rapport factor and methodology factor. On the other hand, some respondents still felt the following negative factors impacted reading fluency in English: Time factor, background factor, materials/resources factor, environmental factor, teacher factor, pupil factor, transition factor, parental factor and policy factor. The discussion in this chapter begins with positive factors and then later will delve into negative factors affecting grade 5 learners' acquisition of reading fluency in English at a selected primary school in Serenje District.

From the paragraph above, one of the positive factors that was highlighted by the respondents was practice factor. This related more to pupils being given chance and opportunity to engage in more and more reading practice. As the adage goes *practice make perfect*. According to respondents, one way in which practice factor could encourage reading fluency was through reading circles, reading competitions and reading clubs as well as Catch Up activities and through creation of a school library. To support and emphasise the issue of more reading practice factor, the following quotation puts it clearly:

The National Reading Panel asserted that fluency is best developed through practice and stressed that this can be accomplished specifically through oral reading practice, such as repeated reading, or guided reading, and through encouraging independent reading as much as possible (Velchik, 2019).

In the same vein, the materials factor could positively affect reading fluency by providing adequate teaching and learning resources (aids), story books and creation of a well-stocked school library. This meant learners did not just need to wait to read during lessons but could do it in their spare time. A library would even enable them borrow books from there as and when need arose. Teacher respondents further commended books and resources from the Step In To English (SITE) course that were used in the previous Primary Reading Programme (PRP) literacy curriculum. Additionally, respondents indicated that videos and audios modelling speaking and reading in English could be used just as some private schools did. This helped motivate learners towards the language they were striving to attain.

The differentiation factor was meant to address the respective individual reading needs and gaps of respective learners.

This meant differentiated teaching occurs when a teacher planned a lesson that adjusted either the content being discussed, the process used to learn or the outcomes expected from learners to ensure that learners at different starting points can receive the instruction they needed to grow and succeed (Lockhart, 2023).

This approach was used extensively outside the normal classroom context as noted by what teachers did during Catch Up sessions with their different learners. These learners were organised in pace groups after conducting a baseline assessment. The idea was to ensure each learner received the appropriate content regardless of the grade. A struggling reader in grade 5 would be doing work in level 1 which was dealing with sounds. Related to this was the methodology factor. In this study, teacher respondents indicated that phonics was very helpful in encouraging learners to know how to read well

in English. This is crucial because one of the skills learners who are beginning to read in English needed was to be motivated on were skills in word recognition and word attack. Showing speaking and reading modelling videos was also crucial in promoting reading fluency. The oral English factor was vital too in promoting reading fluency. As one respondent put it: It is this realisation that made some respondents contend that the language of instruction should be in English as early as possible and in the process code switching could be used to mitigate learners who may not understand the language. The oral language factor is in tandem with scholarly work by Babayigit (2015) who contends that;

Oral language was the strongest predictor of reading comprehension levels in L1 and L2. He noted that the weaker English oral language skills explained the lower performance of L2 learners on reading comprehension. He goes on to suggest that his study results underscored the importance of supporting oral language development in minority language learners.

In the same view, O' Hara et al (2020) aver that there is a clear connection between the development of oral language and literacy.

The teacher factor was also crucial in promoting reading fluency. For example, one respondent emphasised the fact that teacher motivation was very critical in reading fluency. The way a teacher taught or delivered a reading lesson would encourage learners to put in more effort. Related to this aspect was the teacher-pupil rapport factor. The nature of the relationship between individual learners and their teacher played a key role in whether learners would be free to make mistakes as they learnt to read without fear of being scolded or being laughed at or shamed by the teacher him/herself. In other words, the quality of teacher-pupil interaction was vital in achieving reading fluency. According to one of the teacher respondents, learners who have a healthy relationship with their teacher would not want to let down their teacher and so they get motivated to excel. In the same vein, Kaani, et al. (2022) highlighted some of the reasons for dismal standards of literacy attainment in

Zambia. These included a high pupil-teacher ratio at about 49:1, poor resourced learning environments as well as lack of effective supervision.

On the other hand, some respondents still felt the following negative factors impacted reading fluency in English: Time factor, background factor, materials/resources factor, environmental factor, teacher factor, pupil factor, transition factor, parental factor and policy factor.

Firstly, on time factor, teacher respondents hinted that achieving reading fluency was a challenge owing to limited or no time dedicated to reading on the timetable. For example, one of the teacher respondents indicated that learners were sometimes only exposed to reading in some cases at the time they were attempting a comprehension exercise. This made it very difficult to offer individualised attention to each learner to suit his/her needs. Time factor limited learning time and interaction between the learners and their teachers. To support and emphasise the issue of more reading practice and issue of time factor, the following quotation puts it clearly:

There is a direct proportion between the time allocated by readers for reading and the increase of the amount of reading. In order to increase the reading motivation of students, teachers are required to allocate more time for their students with reading difficulties and increase the duration of reading in general (Yildiz, 2013).

Regarding background factor, the concern was that a number of learners particularly those from marginalised rural homes and surrounding villages who were in grade 5 at the time of the study had not had a chance to attend preschool. In short, the learners had no pre-school foundation that would expose them to skills like print awareness among others. This meant teachers had to find a way of bridging the knowledge gap of missed early childhood education opportunities. This is where the Catch Up initiative came in to address such gaps. The issue of materials/resources factor was manifested in limited story and pupils' books at the disposal of teachers and learners. This

compelled teacher to just rely on very short and artificially crafted teacher made decodable stories. Limited materials were compounded by the free education policy pronounced by the Ministry of Education since 2021. This meant the number of learners tended to be more than the material resources allocated to the class. The environmental factor was notable too because some children at the school in question came from the rural or peri-urban area of the study district that had extremely few or no parents as well as older siblings that could support the school's efforts to impart oral or reading skills in English in such learners. These were learners who were probably coming from places where they had never been introduced to any form of English. Reading and understanding what they read was a challenge let alone speaking or understanding certain commands given in English.

Further, the teacher factor arose in form of some teachers only concentrating on learners from very affluent families. The same teachers would give the few reading materials available to learners who were already doing relatively well in reading. Additionally, some respondents indicated that some teachers were not committed to teaching in English and thereby not pushing enough for learners to breakthrough in English too. This in turn perpetuated what is called the Matthew Effect. The Matthew Effect refers to a pattern in which those who begin with advantage accrue more advantage over time and those who begin with disadvantage become more disadvantaged over time (Dannefer, 1987; O'Rand, 1996). The consequence was an ever-increasing gap between the privileged and underprivileged even in the class set-up. Additionally, teachers were reported to have a negative attitude towards handling learners in grades 5-7 seemingly because of cherishing a relaxed manner of teaching learners who were learning in their local language. This view is in tandem with the findings of Kaani (2018) in his study which also noted that teachers were poorly equipped to provide effective literacy instructions due to a pedagogical-content knowledge deficit. This observation tallies yet again with the respondents' views that all of them did not

receive any explicit instructions from their colleges or universities on teaching reading fluency in English.

In the same vein is the pupil factor, this was highlighted by learners either being late for school or completely absent during the time they were expected to report for remedial work during Catch Up lessons or reading circles. This meant that almost each day, teachers would be dealing with different learners from the ones they had the previous day. Additionally, some learners were reported to be timid when asked to read aloud. This was also experienced by the researcher at the time learners were given chance to do a one-on-one one minute reading to rate their Words Per Minute as well as Words Correct Per Minute.

The transition factor refers to what goes on from the time learners' breakthrough reading in the regional official language of the area where they are to the time they begin to attempt to read in English. The respondents' noted that most teachers were carried away by striving to ensure learners read in their local language. As one teacher rightly put it, "*the concentration is done much on teaching learners how to read in Ibibemba (ZL) or any other local language.*" The transition factor is related to the policy factor where the focus was on implementing Zambia's language policy in the education sector. In this vein, the National Literacy Framework (NLF) of 2013 guides as follows:

To support early literacy and later, English literacy instruction, MESVTEE will introduce instruction in a familiar language so as to build learners' arsenal for learning to read in other languages as well as learning content subjects (MESVTEE, 2013, p.5).

One of the teacher respondents indicated that crossing over or transitioning from Ibibemba (ZL) to English was challenging. The assumption by NLF was that learners would just automatically slide into the English mode after breaking through in a familiar language. Unfortunately, this automatic sliding is not happening because there is something which teachers were supposed to do at Grades 2, 3, and 4 which was not happening in the classroom set

up in those grades. For example, in some schools, grade 2s had only a single 30-minute period of Oral English per week while in some cases completely no period for Oral English as observed by Masaiti, Mandyata, Zuilkowski, Kasimba, Meki, Chilufya and Katatisha (2022). Moreover, in multilingual settings like Zambia, it would be necessary that teachers use multilingual language strategies such as translanguaging in order for all learners to access knowledge regardless of their linguistic ability. It is pedagogically recommended that during transition from one language to another, translanguaging be used as a bridge (Banda and Mwanza, 2020; Nyimbili and Mwanza, 2020; Mashinja and Mwanza, 2020; Mwanza, 2020; Mubita and Mwanza, 2020; Banda and Mwanza, 2020; Mwanza and Bwalya, 2019). The last but not the least negative factor noted was parental factor. This had something to do with very unsupportive parents who gave very little or no support to their children or ward regarding reading on its own or task related to reading. This was manifested usually through homework tasks in reading or reading related that were never endorsed by parents or never carried out by the pupil because of the missing parental input at home. These parents also did not even take time to read with their children or ward. To support and emphasise the issue of parental involvement in their children's reading, the following quotation puts it clearly:

Parents reading interactively to their child, co-reading with their child in which the child may read some words or follow along with a finger to the words and turn pages, or having their child read with or to them has been well-evidenced throughout the literature as a highly effective strategy to improve fluency and overall reading skills for younger children (Wundenber, Wyse, & Chaplain, 2013; Mol & Bus, 2011 as cited by Velchik, 2019, p.18).

The findings of this study are in tandem with Chibamba's (2012) research done on ROC for grades 5 in Lusaka. She noted that factors that seemed to have the greatest impact on the low reading levels among Grade 5 pupils learning under Read On Course (ROC) were family, pupil, teacher and school related. Other factors

she cited included lack of ROC materials and classroom libraries, lack of teacher supervision by relevant authorities, teacher and pupil transfers from regions with different language background. Further, teachers and pupils' language background not being in line with language of instruction, new technology, a home environment which did not support continued practice in reading and poor or inadequate training of teachers in literacy teaching. The point of departure with this study's findings is that Chibamba's (2012) study did not categorise her findings into positive and negative factors. Additionally, this study did not get anything about technology factors in its findings.

In the same vein, the findings of this study are similar to those of Kayabasii (2017) who noted five categories of factors contributing to reading difficulties and these were family factors (wrong attitudes in families, financial problems), individual differences (age), education factors (lack of preschool education and not completing homework), emotional factors (attitudes towards reading), and environmental factors (lack of role models, crowded classrooms). Kayabasii's study group comprised 5 classroom teachers working in different classroom levels and occupational experiences from the provinces of Kastamonu and Çankırı in Turkey. Data was collected using the semi-structured interviews. The point of departure for this study is that Kayabasii's study even went further to allude to emotional factors which were not highlighted in this study.

Conclusion

It has been established that learners reading fluency is low. It has been shown that learners are weak in all four aspects of reading fluency namely, accuracy, rate, prosody and comprehension. It has been established that availability of teaching materials, reading practice, rich literacy backgrounds and good teachers quality help some learners achieve high levels of reading fluency while the absence of these factors lead to poor performance among learners.

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